

taken from the top of 100 random tillers at the postflowering stage.

Leaves of tall varieties had wider leaf attachment angles than dwarf varieties (see figure). The difference is clear in the second and third leaves. But all leaves of Lalnakanda had closer angles than did dwarf varieties. Incorporation of acute leaf attachment angle in short-leaved dwarfs could result in better plant types where light interception would be less. Plant populations per unit area could be increased without adversely affecting photosynthetic rates. The trait is linked with a simply inherited rudimentary juncture condition and could be incorporated easily into the desired plant type. ■

Angles of leaf attachment of different rice varieties observed at Bhagalpur, India.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Grain quality

A preliminary study on the specific gravity of rice grain

B. D. Peiris and D. Senadhira, Central Rice Breeding Station, Batalagoda, Ibbagamuwa, Sri Lanka

Most Sri Lankans prefer red rices. But with the introduction of high yielding varieties, the number of red rice varieties in cultivation has decreased considerably. A preliminary study used specific gravity to compare rice color and grain weight.

Twenty rice varieties (10 red and 10 white), including both recommended varieties and elite lines, were grown under identical conditions during the 1980 dry season. Rice yield was dried in the shade to 14% moisture. Fifteen-gram samples from both brown rice and polished rice were drawn. Grain weight was determined by the specific gravity bottle method using kerosene oil.

Results suggest that the specific gravity of white rice is significantly higher than that of red rice (see table). Polishing increased the specific gravity, which could be attributed to removal of the high fat content of the bran.

Yield is the primary objective in varie-

tal improvement work in Sri Lanka. It is possible that the reduction in the number of red rice varieties grown is due to an unconscious selection against red grains, which have a lower weight than white. ■

Specific gravity measurements of rice in Sri Lanka.

Specific gravity ^a			
Red rice		White rice	
Brown	Polished	Brown	Polished
1.4000	1.4260	1.4120	1.4390

t-value ^b for color (red & white):

Brown rice = 2.942**

Polished rice = 3.106**

Milling (brown & polished):

Red rice = 5.733**

White rice = 5.978**

^a Mean of 10 samples. ^b **significant at .01 level.

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Breeding high-quality and high-yielding varieties of rice in Afghanistan

S. S. Saini, rice breeder, Indian Agricultural Assistance Programme in Afghanistan, Embassy of India, Kabul, Afghanistan

Rice consumers in Afghanistan are quality conscious. Local varieties are high quality, with long, slender, translucent grains that cook into excellent plaw or biriani. Two very popular varieties, Barah and Lawangin, are grown extensively in the northern and the eastern areas. They are tall growing with weak straw and poor response to fertilization; hence productivity is low.

To increase yield potential, the two local varieties were crossed with a high yielding culture; IR790-28, at IRRI. Bulk seed for growing the F₃ was received in 1973. Selection of desirable recombinants was carried out in F₃ to F₆ plants grown under high-level fertility (120-60-60 kg NPK/ha) at the Pos-i-Shan Agricultural Research Station at Baghlan.

Thirty high-yielding cultures from IR790-28/Barah and 37 cultures from IR790-28/Lawangin met the quality